

Identifying Vulnerabilities in a Website Using Uniscan and Comparing Uniscan, Grabber, Nikto

Sneha Varghese

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
snehavarghese2021@mca.ajce.in

Rini Kurian

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
rinikurian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract : The research paper demonstrates that in these days websites or system are phased many type of security issues. so vulnerability scanning tools are essential to detect the security risk of a system and its impact on the whole organization. Many number of vulnerability testing tools are reported and used based on the security requirement of a firm. In this paper aims how to identify the vulnerabilities in a website using uniscan tool and what vulnerabilities can be identified. and also we compare and analyse the vulnerability test results of 3 tools uniscan, nikto, grabber, using their urls from the security blogs and literature, it is observed that grabber is useful not fast but portable really adaptable, and then nikto is quick and suitable for surface level scan, however, the uniscan works better than any vulnerability scanner such as nikto, grabber and it performs detailed testing which includes data base test such as sql injection. and that is in this paper we find out which of these tool are best for checking for vulnerabilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of computer technology, now security of the website is very important this is because website contain all kinds of essentials of a company. and nowadays it is very easy for hackers to attack any websites. we face today man made attacks and similarly. vulnerability is weakness or misconfiguration in a website or web application code it will help for attackers to gain the control of the sites. Sql injection, cross site scripting(xss), php injection etc are the most familiar vulnerabilities. penetration testing is the one of the best method for find vulnerabilities. In the following sections, we discuss about how to find vulnerabilities in best way, what is the vulnerabilities and describe about web application tools. In the one section we explain about uniscan tool. Uniscan is a free penetration testing tool. and it is one of the best tool for test web application vulnerabilities including sql injections, cross site scripting(xss), php injection, remote file inclusion(RFI), local file inclusion(LFI), remote command execution, web shell vulnerabilities, and backup files on the target web application. In the next section includes some

another tools for comparing with uniscan tool, that tools are NIKTO and GRABBER. Nikto is another scanning tool. is a free software command line vulnerability scanner. it scans dangerous files/CGIs, outdated server software and other issues. Grabber is a web application scanner and it is designed to scan small websites such as personals. The final section we conclude the result which one is the best tool for comparing in these three tools.

II. WEB VULNERABILITY

Web application vulnerabilities involve a system flaw or weakness in a web-based application. web applications need to interact with multiple users across multiple networks, and that level of accessibility is easily taken advantage of by hackers.

Some of the vulnerabilities are:

- Sql injection
- Cross-site scripting

Sql injection : structured query language (sql) is a language designed to manipulate and manage data in a database. it is a type of cybersecurity attack. it will be target these databases using specifically crafted sql statements to trick the systems into doing unexpected and undesired things.

Actions a successful attacker may take on a compromised target include:

- Bypassing authentication
- Exfiltrating /stealing data
- Modifying or corrupting data
- Deleting data
- Running arbitrary code
- Gaining root access to the system itself

Cross-site scripting(xss): cross-site scripting attacks can significantly damage a web company's reputation by placing the users information at risk without any indication that anything malicious even

occurred. when a webpage is compromised with cross-site scripting, a collection of issues can quickly emerge. possible concerns include, but are not limited to:

- Sensitive user data being exposed
- Attackers seizing online accounts and impersonating users
- Vandalism of website content presentation
- Upload of malicious ‘trojen horse’ programs
- Redirect of web pages to harmful locations

III. WEB VULNERABILITY DETECTOR

The web vulnerability scanners are opted to find distinctive vulnerabilities in web applications. Following are the details of various web vulnerability detectors

a) uniscan

Uniscan is a efficient web vulnerability scanner that mainly focused at information security to detect stringent vulnerabilities in web systems and is authorized under the GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENCE 3.0.it will be writtern in perl .this tool will test many vulnerabilities. That vulnerabilities listed below

- Local file include(LFI)
- Remote command execution(RCE)
- Remote file include(RFI)
- Cross-site scripting(XSS)
- Sql and blind sql injection

The characteristics of uniscan scanner are as:

- use of threads in the crawler and Identification of system pages through a Web Crawler .
- Control to many requests and Identification of variation of system pages by web crawler
- file extensions are controlled and that are ignored.
- Test of pages found via the GET and POST method.
- Support for SSL requests (HTTPS) and proxy.
- Generate site list using Google and bing.
- Plug-in support for Crawler, dynamic tests, static tests and for stress tests .

the primary advantages of uniscan net scanner are itsbriefinstallationandstartingup of several sensors which might be effortlessly linked via flat cables and an additional faraway control permit sensors.

TheYAdaptor offers a simple cabling solution with most effective one cable for two sensors on each aspects of the door. the 2 door loop sets DLP 6 and Door Loop offer a easy connection to the wall [17]. Its trying out technique that can be selected according with the respective drive sorts and not using a interference through synchronization of the optics and we can for my part turning off of single beams.

- It can also perform more detailed server fingerprinting by using the -j option — simply append it to the end of the command.
- This will run a ping test and traceroute to determine the network connectivity status, followed by an nslookup (name server lookup) to obtain any DNS records that are available.
- This option will also kick off an Nmap scan to discover any open services and ports, so be aware of the target as some defenses will consider this aggressive.

Figure :1 uniscan working

- It should be noted that in the command line version multiple options can also be set at the same time, like so: **uniscan -u http://172.16.1.102 -qwds**

Uniscan also saves each scan as an HTML file under **/usr/share/uniscan/report/** if scan results are needed at a later time.

Figure :2 result of uniscan

We can also enable some static checks on the target with the -s option. This will run tests that detect local file include, remote command execution, and remote file include vulnerabilities.

Figure:3 working options of uniscan

b) Nikto

Nikto is a powerful internet utility vulnerability scanner. This is designed to research an internet server to discover excessive security issues or flaws. Identifying protection problems proactively, and solving them, is an essential step closer to verifying the safety of the web server [1]. Joggling Nikto on a normal basis will confirm that you become aware of common issues for your web server or net programs. Nikto is absolutely open source and is written in Perl. It's miles a non-invasive scanner that runs at the command line, with none graphical user interface. It is ideal for running the tool remotely over SSH connections [1, 13]. If you have net servers allocate CGI scripts, Nikto may be an efficient aid for auditing the safety of these net servers and packages.

It supports SSL, full http proxy, text, HTML, XML and CSV to store reviews. It could experiment for more than one ports and server through taking inputs from documents like nmapoutput.it's far successful enough to perceive hooked up software program with headers, files and favicons. It can authenticate hosts with basic and NTLM and Scans can be automobile-paused at detailed time. It could be included in Nessus and is routinely configured to release Nikto whilst it reveals a specific internet server. It could be able to sending records along with requests to servers (move site scripting and sq. injection) [31]. It could test tuning to encompass or exclude complete training of vulnerability exams and additionally wagert to uchy records for authorization geographical region that includes many default identification/pw combos. Authorization guessing shafts any directory, no longer just the rootlisting. It can enhance the fake superb reduction through a couple of measures like headers, web page content, and content hashing [31].

Following are the list of Vulnerabilities scan by nikto scanner

1. Server and software miss configuration
2. Default files and programs
3. Insecure files and programs
4. Outdated servers and programs [13, 14]

c) Grabber

It is an open source web application locator that aids in recognizing security escape clauses in web applications. It performs sweeps to recognize the weaknesses like cross site prearranging, SQL infusion, Ajax testing, reinforcement record check and then some. It's a very basic and versatile

scanner which is for the most part utilized for little web applications and it additionally doesn't offer any GUI interface. It can handle the JavaScript records, parse it to recover the worker side's contents names and attempts to snatch some particular boundaries name. This apparatus is principally useful for individual use and no sort of expert reason. It is written in Python, and its source code is likewise accessible which can be adjusted according to necessities.

Its highlights incorporates Cross-Site Scripting, an exceptional Blind SQL Injection module, File Inclusion and Backup records check, Straightforward AJAX check It can parse each JavaScript and snatch the URL and attempt to get the boundaries. It likewise has Hybrid examination/Crystal ball testing for PHP application utilizing PHP SAT, JavaScript source code analyzer, Generation of a record [session_id, time (t)] for next details examination

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

on this section, we implement Nikto, Uniscan and grabber a web vulnerability detection tools on, linux running gadget that detect several web vulnerabilities inclusive of sql injection, XSSattack, Remote code execution, blind sql,and javascript code test for internet based application .

the following table:1compares the the special internet scanners for the one of a kind vulnerabilities.

As visible from the table: 1, grabber and uniscan vulnerability scanner that has detected most of the particular vulnerabilities followed through nikto scanner. In various vulnerability scanners like grabber, nikto and uniscan are opted to detect the various web based vulnerabilities.

Table no:1 comparing

Vulnerabilities	Nikto	Uniscan	Grabber
Sql injection	No	Yes	Yes
Cross site scripting	Yes	Yes	Yes
Remote code execution	No	Yes	No
Rogue server	Yes	No	No
Blind Sql injection	No	Yes	Yes
Local file includes	No	Yes	No

File insert include	No	No	Yes
JavaScript code	No	No	Yes

V. CONCLUSION

Web applications have the most basic approach to give admittance to online administrations. A most flourishing impediment is customer side assaults in which dubious programming is naturally introduced on the person's machine. In this paper, we investigate different web vulnerability weaknesses through web vulnerability scanners. Weakness appraisal assumes a huge part in getting the network framework. Our experimentation on web weaknesses show that distinctive web scanners distinguish diverse sort of weaknesses however not a solitary instrument is as productive to distinguishing a wide range of web vulnerability. This paper addressed various tools opted for scanning web vulnerabilities and their comparative analysis. We identified that what vulnerabilities a specific tool is efficient to detect by running various web applications on each tool. Grabber and uniscan tool has many significant features including within it that are not present in other tools i.e. nikto, The vulnerabilities such as file insertion attack, local file include and blind sql injection are not present in other tools and hence can be indulged with the other tool that works differently and produces distinctive results.

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